

SOCIAL SCIENCES

GLOBALIZATION: NATIONAL SECURITY PROBLEM IN AZERBAIJAN UNDER GLOBAL CLIMATE CHANGE

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Abstract

In the article, as the high development of globalization, integration and information technology processes impose new obligations, as a result of new realities and events taking place on the basis of national interests, the necessity of the specification of internal and external threats to the Republic of Azerbaijan, more efficient, purposeful, flexible implementation of complex and consistent measures to ensure national interests is analyzed. Additionally, the article is dedicated to the critical importance of combating transnational crimes, such as terrorism, aggression, and separatism, as well as religious and political extremism, the illegal trafficking of drugs, radioactive substances, weapons, and human trafficking. This issue is extremely important to all countries in the world, including the Republic of Azerbaijan. At the same time, the article discusses and analyzes the declaration of 2024 as the "Green World Solidarity Year" in Azerbaijan and the hosting of the COP29 international event.

Keywords: Globalization, global security, global terrorism, social media, national security, national interest, Republic of Azerbaijan, Contract of the Century, South Caucasus, Shusha Declaration, Karabakh Declaration.

Introduction. Although the term "globalization" was introduced into academic discourse in 1983 by Harvard University professor Theodore Levitt, it was first used in 1944. In fact, globalization began with the development of transportation and communication, which allowed isolated peoples to connect with one another since ancient times. For example, the domestication of many animals (such as horses, dogs, camels, etc.) and the development of ships and boats led to isolated peoples engaging in various types of relationships with one another. These relationships did not always align with the will and interests of those peoples. For centuries, ideas, cultures, and forms of art belonging to different nations have spread from one part of the world to another. Even in the Middle Ages, the peoples living in different regions of the world had very superficial perceptions of each other. During this period, very few people traveled from one continent to another. Such journeys not only required a long time but were also dangerous to human life in many cases. In the modern era, however, it only takes a few days to fully circle the Earth. Not only states but also legal entities use these opportunities in their work activities, and ordinary people also use the opportunities offered by social networks and the internet to stay in touch and exchange information of various kinds. In short, with the process of globalization, the world is taking on a uniform social appearance. Of course, the opportunities provided by Scientific and Technical Progress undoubtedly play an important role in this process. As the opportunities provided by Scientific and Technical Progress increase in the future, the process of globalization will deepen further. It should be noted that globalization is the opening of financial resources, products, services, technology, and jobs from a local framework to the world. In recent times, a wide variety of research works have been written and published in the field of globalization, both in Azerbaijan and in foreign countries. The strengthening

of globalization on a global scale also creates conditions for the rise of global crimes and moral degradation. The prevalence of drug addiction worldwide, the operation of organized crime on an international scale, and the activities of mafias and international terrorism can be cited as examples. All of this shows that the issue of globalization is not a straightforward phenomenon. "In modern conditions, terrorist activities are expanding their operations in close connection with international terrorist centers and organizations, disregarding state borders. One of the most pressing issues facing the international community today is the implementation of effective measures against the threat of terrorism. The importance of combating crimes related to international terrorism was reflected in the Declaration adopted at the Millennium Summit held in New York from September 6 to 8, 2000. This document emphasized the need for the coordination of actions by 192 states in the fight against international terrorism, as well as the necessity for the international community to provide support to the United Nations in effectively combating terrorism in the future" [6.p.197].

Thus, as a result of this process, the world is becoming a unified place. The world is coming closer in terms of time and space. This proximity manifests itself as information. We become aware of events happening in the world through the internet. Additionally, the borders between countries are losing their significance. In a globalizing world, threats based on global security have begun to surpass national security. A new system of global relations has simultaneously created a chain of virtual relationships. With the increase in the number of internet users, lasting concepts and values have started to form within virtual relationships. "In 1995, there were 16 million internet users worldwide, while by 2000, this number had risen to 360 million, and in the following 12 years, it reached 2.5 billion. Between

2000 and 2012, there was a 566% increase in the number of internet users" [11]. In 2018, this number reached 5 billion. Virtual relationships demand the creation of virtual security networks and new forms and rules for controlling mass social information networks. All of this requires expenditures that exceed the capabilities of any single state. Consequently, there is a need for the emergence of new global rules and concepts of security.

With the advent of social media, the concepts of "soft power" and "soft threats" have also gained relevance. The connection of social media tools to global structures allows certain powers to use these networks to convey and impose their ideas on the other side, resulting in inequalities in the understanding of global security. Alongside global relations, global competition is also expanding. The "great power diplomacy," debt traps, and strategies to interfere in the backyard of other global powers pursued by certain states, especially China, have created new non-traditional norms of security. In parallel, the globalization of the Chinese military, based on international and technological innovations, has led to the emergence of unique new norms of security. Artificial intelligence, space technologies, and 5G (communication technology) are breaking the boundaries of traditional security and creating unilateral new rules and concepts. Accordingly, changes in investment relations, the globalization of e-commerce, large loans allocated to small and weak states, the establishment of investment banks within this framework, and the emergence of various models of white networking and countless similar methods are not without effect on the meanings and mechanisms of national security. As all of this unfolds, the continuation of traditional structures of national security alongside global mechanisms, as seen in the Chinese model, reflects internal closure, the application of violence against minorities, and the classification of groups with different thoughts and beliefs as threats. This paradox also reflects that the boundaries of security are changing in accordance with the interests of powers in the global arena. With the emergence of all these developments, global legal platforms and concepts are losing their scope. However, when the U.S. announced its national security doctrine, it recognized law as a fundamental binding force and considered it the main condition for international peace. In the transition from a "state of security" to "maintaining security," the protection of individuals and society from emerging threats, the exercise of human rights and freedoms, and the active role of people in this process formed the legal framework of the U.S. national security concept. From this position, the U.S. has, in some cases, exhibits strong reactions against political regimes and states. After the events of September 11, it became clear that, in many instances, international law was ineffective in the U.S.'s policy of considering security a global issue.

Traditional national security structures were under the control of the state. These structures were primarily carried out by police organizations, gendarmerie forces, military units, and security agencies. They played a regulatory role in maintaining the internal security of each state. These organized forces were regulated not only

by the state's own laws but also in accordance with international legal norms. The fundamental principle of international law (*raison d'être*) and its interactions is based on the characteristics and needs of the international political order. Within this order, there should be common terms on how to coexist in various forms or how to respond in cases of global adversaries. Although these views may seem scattered and diverse, the international legal system has successfully formed certain distinctive frameworks [8. p.31-32]. It is a reality that states need law to achieve certain goals such as security, economic productivity, and ideological dominance. The International Court of Justice, established in 1949, affirmed its existence as an object of international law within the framework of the United Nations. At the same time, the Food and Agriculture Organization has the right to examine international order according to the same standards worldwide. In other words, states must act in accordance with the security principles set by international law, alongside their own security regulations. The problem lies not in the measures and standards defined by international law, but in the lack of consistent enforcement of these legal principles across all countries. For example, the violence against the Muslim minority in Myanmar in recent years has not been assessed within the framework of international justice law. This reflects how international law is subject to the influence and pressure of states. M. Hart and A. Negri, from this perspective, express the idea that "law (by replicating many forms that money assumes in the capitalist system) carries no inherent value in itself, but consists of the values produced daily by social efforts, the necessary conditions for the reproduction of capitalist society, the division of labor, and colonialism" [4. p. 22]. This view arises not from the issues raised by international law itself, but from the world system to which the law is tied. Modern international law, as a product of a specific state, traces its origins back to the periods when capitalist production dominated. The process of creating international law largely followed the emergence of capitalist states after monarchical ones. Therefore, since international law itself is based on securing capitalist production relations, it is not fully capable of ensuring the overall security of the world [9. p. 19-20].

It should be noted that the primary drivers of globalization are the economically, politically, socially, culturally, and technologically developed countries of the world. We wouldn't be wrong to say that these nations shape the future of the world. In the current context, where the rapid pace of global political processes and the difficulty in predicting future prospects prevail, the study of national security policies of states is one of the most pressing issues. The expansion of global processes in the modern era highlights the importance of diplomatic relations in ensuring the security of states. In this regard, the study of the national security of the Republic of Azerbaijan, as it integrates into the global community in the context of globalization, holds significant importance. In the 1990s, global changes that occurred in the world impacted both the international and domestic situation of the Republic of Azerbaijan. As a

result, it became impossible to carry out effective reforms in the country without considering the new global geopolitical landscape. Since national security is a matter of strategic importance, it is necessary to link theoretical generalizations with practical solutions to address the issue. Because of the strength of national leader Heydar Aliyev's diplomacy, Azerbaijan achieved the only viable path to ensuring external security—a balance between its own interests and those of other countries, along with agreements within the framework of international security. The "Law of the Republic of Azerbaijan on National Security," dated June 29, 2004, No. 712-IIQ, outlines the legal foundations aimed at the development of Azerbaijan as an independent, sovereign, and democratic state, including conceptual provisions regarding the threat of terrorism and effective countermeasures. The law designates international terrorism as a primary threat to the national security of the Republic of Azerbaijan. Accordingly, the implementation of international cooperation in the fight against international terrorism and transnational crime has been identified as a key measure for ensuring the country's national security [1]. The law on "National Security" of the Republic of Azerbaijan holds significant importance in addressing the gaps in this area. It outlines key issues related to the provision of national security, including the identification of internal and external threats, the issuance of warnings about these threats, and the implementation of operational measures to neutralize them. Additionally, the law emphasizes the assurance of sovereignty and territorial integrity, the maintenance and support of a sufficiently high level of military potential, the detection and prevention of foreign intelligence and subversive activities, and effective measures for warning and prevention. It also highlights the strengthening of the state's role as a guarantor of the security of society and individuals, as well as the expansion of mutually beneficial international cooperation in the sphere of security. The principles essential for ensuring the national security of the Republic of Azerbaijan include legality, adherence to state interests, the responsibility of the state in ensuring security, integration into international security systems, and the unity, interrelation, and balance of all types of security.

It should be noted that the sources of Azerbaijan's national security consist of the Constitution of the Republic of Azerbaijan, the law on "National Security," the National Security Concept, the Military Doctrine, presidential decrees, and other normative acts of the Republic of Azerbaijan, as well as international treaties and agreements concluded and ratified by the Republic of Azerbaijan.

In 1991, the law on the Ministry of National Security (MNS) was established, followed by the law on state secrets in 1996, the law on defense in 1997, the decree on the establishment of an academy under the MNS in 1999, and the law on intelligence and counter-intelligence in 2004, along with other relevant legal documents reflecting the principles of ensuring Azerbaijan's national security. Azerbaijan's national security is ensured through the consistent implementation of na-

tional security policy using the political, economic, legal, military, organizational, and other means at the country's disposal. The formation and implementation of the national security policy of the Republic of Azerbaijan involve the participation of the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan, the Milli Majlis, the Government of the Republic of Azerbaijan, the Security Council of the Republic of Azerbaijan, the State Security Service of the Republic of Azerbaijan, executive authorities, and judicial bodies.

The participation of the Republic of Azerbaijan in global processes, its rising economic potential, and the successful continuation of its energy policy are significant factors in ensuring its national security. "In the modern era, energy security has emerged as a fundamental issue for world states. The minimization of foreign energy dependence has become a crucial condition not only for the national security of individual states but also for their ability to pursue independent policies. The Baku-Tbilisi-Ceyhan oil pipeline and the Baku-Tbilisi-Erzurum gas pipeline are strategically important projects that significantly contribute to the economic and energy security of both the Republic of Azerbaijan and Europe as a whole. The integration of Central Asian states with these transit routes in the near future will further enhance Azerbaijan's role in the energy supply and security of the West" [5.p.69]. The "Contract of the Century" significantly drew the attention of major powers and developed states towards Azerbaijan, particularly due to the joint exploitation of hydrocarbon resources in the Caspian Sea. Among the key projects, the role of TRASEKA as a West-East transport corridor is undeniable. This signifies the integration of the national transportation system with European and global transportation networks. Investments made under the Great Silk Road program and the increase in international freight traffic directly influence the political and geopolitical landscape in the Caucasus region. The expansion of Azerbaijan's connections with the international community not only fosters progressive technologies and trade relations with developed countries but also accelerates significant capital investments and the influx of investors into the country. This situation reflects the existence of a favorable environment for development in Azerbaijan. The establishment of free economic zones (FEZ) plays a significant role in Azerbaijan's participation in globalization processes. Since 1994, the country has made advancements in this area through active cooperation with various international and regional organizations. Azerbaijan's position in the globalization processes is closely linked to the main directions of its foreign policy, its geopolitical approaches, and its relationships with international organizations that meet modern requirements. Azerbaijan's diplomacy has achieved positive results by pursuing a pragmatic and balanced policy, establishing and developing cooperative relations with neighboring countries and major powers (with the exception of Armenia). Thus, a positive conclusion can be drawn about the place and role of our country in the context of globalization. The strategic geographical position of the Republic of Azerbaijan in the Eurasian region, its foreign

policy, and commitment to democratic principles ensure the country's involvement in the globalization process, providing broad opportunities to benefit from the advantages it offers to our nation. Just as there are supporters of globalization (globalists), there are also opponents (anti-globalists). Both supporters and opponents of this process base their arguments on the positive and negative impacts of globalization on the material conditions of people in various regions of the world. In this regard, researchers Hasan Alibayli and Fuzuli Mammadli write in their article "The Phenomenon of Globalization, Its Essence and Development Dynamics": "Opponents of globalization view this process from the perspective of the national state's loss of its significant role and the facilitation of foreign interventions, arguing that globalization keeps people under pressure, undermines the power of states, subjects all issues to the hegemony of imperialist states, destroys national values, oppresses the weak, widens the gap between the rich and the poor, generates immense profits solely for transnational corporations, enables these corporations to 'strangle' developing countries, and disrupts the ecological balance of the planet".

Supporters of globalization, on the other hand, emphasize the positive aspects of this process, claiming that it will assist in solving many humanitarian problems that are sources of planetary threat. According to them, it is precisely the result of the more intensive character of globalization that the main actors in international relations—states and international organizations—are working together to address global problems and engage in effective cooperation. This, in turn, eliminates restrictions that could hinder economic cooperation between states and facilitates the free flow of international investment. Furthermore, it opens up broad opportunities for the protection of human rights and freedoms, as well as the development of democracy" [3.p.653].

In a globalizing world, the formation of a global information network has led to the mutual influence of various national cultures. While this widespread process has positive aspects, it also presents negative features that are foreign to our national mentality and culture, which deal a heavy blow to the unique system of customs and traditions and behavioral models that the Azerbaijani people have developed over the centuries. It should be noted that due to globalization serving the interests of the world's developed giant states and embracing cosmopolitanism, the commitment to our national and spiritual values must be further strengthened. Given its geographical location, Azerbaijan is a region where the interests of the world's power centers collide, making it a region most affected by the transformative processes brought about by globalization. The widespread nature of globalization highlights the issues of strengthening independent Azerbaijan and its place and role among world states. "The security issue is particularly significant for the Republic of Azerbaijan, located in a space where the national interests of many states intersect. Therefore, since regaining independence for the second time in the 20th century, organizing the security of individuals, society, and the state, as well as implementing measures for integration into the global

security system, have become important tasks in state-building" [5.p.21].

It is known that the South Caucasus, as a geopolitical region, falls within the sphere of interests of the Russian Federation, Türkiye, Iran, leading European states, the superpower United States, and China. All of this directly indicates the significance of the South Caucasus on both regional and international levels. It is worth noting that the collapse of the former Soviet Union was accompanied by the emergence of new conflict hotspots in the region. During this time, conflicts arose, such as the Transnistrian conflict in the former Soviet Republic of Moldova, the Georgian-Abkhaz and Georgian-Ossetian conflicts in the Republic of Georgia, and the Armenia-Azerbaijan conflict, which stemmed from Armenia's territorial claims and resulted in military aggression against Azerbaijan. The Armenia-Azerbaijan conflict was initiated by Armenia's unjust claims against Azerbaijani territories, supported by Armenia and its international backers. In the late 1980s, as a result of Armenia's open territorial claims on Azerbaijan's historical lands, the provocations it carried out on ethnic grounds, and its acts of separatist terrorism, thousands of our compatriots and military personnel were brutally murdered. Tens of thousands of our citizens were left disabled and injured. Among these tragedies, the most horrifying was the Khojaly genocide perpetrated on the night of February 25 to 26, 1992. The Khojaly genocide committed by Armenians is an example of the most gross and brutal violation of human rights and freedoms, which has been reflected in numerous internationally accepted documents. These documents unequivocally condemn Armenia's aggression against Azerbaijan and the brutal killing of civilians in Khojaly. "The day of Khojaly's occupation is one of the bloodiest pages of Armenian terrorism and the genocide policy against Azerbaijanis. On that day alone, 613 peaceful residents, mostly elderly people, women, and children, were brutally killed, and 1,275 were taken captive. During this mass slaughter and act of vandalism, 56 individuals were killed with special cruelty and ruthlessness, burned alive, decapitated, or had their skin peeled off, and pregnant women were stabbed to death. Of those injured, 487 were left disabled, including 76 minors" [10.p.105-106]. During the tragedy, the fate of 150 of those taken captive remains unknown to this day.

The former USSR leadership did not prevent this conflict; rather, they provided direct and indirect support to Armenia. This was because both peoples were striving for independence and freedom. The struggle for liberation of the nations did not satisfy the former USSR leadership. "As a result, a conflict that could have been completely resolved in its initial stage gradually escalated into a full-scale confrontation between the two peoples, transforming into a large-scale war." [7.p.204-205]. The Armenia-Azerbaijan conflict has entered the history of the 20th century as one of the most tragic conflicts, with its consequences significantly impacting the fate of millions of Azerbaijanis. Two hundred thousand people were displaced from the present-day Republic of Armenia, and over one million Azerbaijani citizens became refugees and internally

displaced persons from their ancestral homes. On May 12, 1994, a declaration was adopted between the parties to the conflict to halt Armenia's aggressive war against Azerbaijan—a ceasefire was established. Despite twenty-six years of negotiations aimed at a peaceful resolution of the conflict following the ceasefire, Azerbaijani territories were not liberated from occupation. The United Nations resolutions 822, 853, 874, and 884, which called for the unconditional withdrawal of the occupying Armenia from the occupied Azerbaijani territories, were not implemented. The failure of the peace process in resolving the conflict can be attributed to various reasons, (lack of overlapping national interests of many states) as well as the historical-psychological and political situation of the Armenian side.

In April 2016, the clashes known as the "Four-Day War" occurred, during which the Azerbaijani Armed Forces liberated part of the occupied territories and some strategic heights from enemy forces. This event played a significant role in boosting the fighting spirit of the Azerbaijani Armed Forces and strengthening the position of Azerbaijani diplomacy. Following the April battles, on May 16, 2016, a favorable political and legal environment emerged during the negotiations organized by the USA, France, and Russia in Vienna regarding the resolution of the conflict between Armenia and Azerbaijan. Unfortunately, it did not yield positive results. During this period, those in political power in Armenia—leaders of the separatist military formations in the occupied Azerbaijani territories, who were responsible for the deaths of thousands of Azerbaijanis and were perpetrators of the Khojaly massacre, the "Karabakh Clan" such as R.Kocharian and S.Sargsyan—deliberately prolonged the resolution of the conflict.

On September 27, 2020, in response to Armenia's provocative actions, the victorious Azerbaijani Army launched a counter-offensive, restoring its territorial integrity over the course of 44 days. As is known, on November 10, 2020, at 00:00 Moscow time, a trilateral statement was signed between the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan, Ilham Aliyev, the Prime Minister of the Republic of Armenia, Nikol Pashinyan, and the President of the Russian Federation, Vladimir Putin, regarding the complete cessation of all military operations.

The signing of the November 10 statement signifies Armenia's military capitulation. The statement put an end to years of occupation. According to the agreement, the districts of Aghdam, Lachin, and Kalbajar were returned without bloodshed. Azerbaijan compelled Russia to "correct" its policies in the South Caucasus. The November 10 statement established and mandated the joint monitoring of Türkiye and Russia, which disrupted the traditional stereotypes of Russia's peacekeeping functions in regions like Transnistria, Abkhazia, and Tskhinvali.

Türkiye-Azerbaijan cooperation, friendship, and brotherhood reached its highest level. Türkiye has proven to be a stabilizing factor in the South Caucasus. On June 15, 2021, a historic document, the Shusha Declaration, was signed between the Republic of Azerbaijan and the Republic of Türkiye in Shusha city. The

signing of this document, which encompasses all areas of life for both brotherly countries, holds immense significance for the present and future of both states. This Declaration is an expression of the indomitable will of a brotherly nation, symbolizing the joy of friends and the serious concern of enemies. New realities were created for the political and economic development of neighboring states. Favorable conditions emerged for Türkiye's relations with the Turkic world, as well as for rail and highway connectivity with Azerbaijan. Security was ensured in the South Caucasus and throughout the region. Conditions were established for social, economic, and ethnocultural development. Azerbaijan realized its power in the South Caucasus through military-political and diplomatic means. A fertile ground was formed for economic relations between Azerbaijan, Türkiye, Russia, Iran, Georgia, and possibly Armenia. Instead of laying down their arms and surrendering, the unrecognized separatist regime and its so-called leaders in the Karabakh economic region fell into delusions again. The enforcement of the provisions of the trilateral statement, the prevention of large-scale provocations in the Karabakh economic region, the disarmament and withdrawal of Armenian armed forces from our territories, the neutralization of their military infrastructure, and the protection of the safety of returning civilians and military personnel involved in restoration and reconstruction efforts necessitated the implementation of local counter-terrorism measures in the region to restore the constitutional order of the Republic of Azerbaijan. Additionally, on the morning of September 19, 2023, after six individuals, including four police officers and two civilians, were killed due to a mine explosion in Khojavend, the Azerbaijani state labeled this as a "terror act" and initiated military operations on the same day. The counter-terrorism operations, which lasted for 24 hours (23 hours and 43 minutes), ceased after the surrender of the separatist regime in Karabakh. The unrecognized authority in Karabakh expressed readiness to lay down arms and meet in the city of Yevlakh under Azerbaijan's conditions. Subsequently, the military units of the Armenian armed forces located in the Karabakh region and the illegal Armenian separatist armed groups surrendered, withdrew from combat positions, and fully disarmed, leaving our territory. Simultaneously, contacts were established between official Baku and representatives of Karabakh Armenians, with discussions held in Yevlakh and Khojaly regarding the reintegration of Armenian residents into Azerbaijani society.

On July 6, 2024, an informal summit of the Organization of Turkic States was held in the city of Shusha, initiated by the Republic of Azerbaijan, focusing on the topic of "Building a Sustainable Future through Transport, Connectivity, and Climate Action." The summit was attended by representatives from Azerbaijan, Türkiye, Kazakhstan, Uzbekistan, Kyrgyzstan, Hungary, the Turkish Republic of Northern Cyprus, and the Secretary General of the Turkic States Organization. During the summit, the Karabakh Declaration was signed. This declaration emphasizes the cultural and economic-political integration of the countries within the organization, as well as their collective

strength in geopolitical and security matters on a global scale. The significance of holding the summit in Shusha, a city that was named the "Cultural Capital of the Turkic World" in 2023, carries important historical and political weight. The restoration of the territorial integrity of the Republic of Azerbaijan, along with its increasing political and economic influence, has positioned it as a key player not only in the regional arena but also on the global stage.

Thus, as a result of the anti-terror operation, the Azerbaijani state achieved its territorial integrity. As stated in our constitution, the territory of the "Republic of Azerbaijan is united, inviolable, and indivisible" as a democratic, legal, secular, and unitary republic [2].

Currently, the process of delimiting borders between Armenia and Azerbaijan is ongoing. One of the main issues in the peace negotiations with Armenia is the matter of enclaves. As we know, seven villages (Yukhari Askipara, Ashaghi Askipara, Baghanis Ayrim, Khayrimli, Gyzylhacılı, Sofulu, Barkhudarli) in the Qazakh region and the Karki village in the Sadarak region are under Armenian occupation. According to the agreement reached on April 19, 2024, by the commission for the delimitation of the Azerbaijan-Armenia border, four of the seven villages in the Qazakh region (Bağanis Ayrim, Aşağı Əskipara, Xeyrimli, and Qızılhacılı), which had been under occupation for 30 years, are to be returned to Azerbaijan on May 24, 2024. Now, the section of the border with Armenia, measuring 12.7 km, is not just a conditional border but a real border line that is mutually recognized. The delimitation process continues. The fulfillment of the obligation by the Armenian government to open the Zangezur corridor would not only contribute to the socio-economic development of Azerbaijan and Armenia but also of the entire South Caucasus region.

Today, the Azerbaijani flag is waving in all territories liberated from occupation. Construction and renovation works are underway in these areas, with new roads and communication lines being established. After 30 years, refugees and internally displaced persons are returning to their ancestral homes. During the occupation, Armenia looted and destroyed Azerbaijan's national and cultural heritage, razed cities and other settlements, and caused significant ecological damage to the region. Hundreds of thousands of mines and explosive devices have been buried in Azerbaijani lands. Armenia will not be able to evade legal responsibility for the numerous war crimes, acts of mass murder and genocide, terrorist activities, and vandalism committed against Azerbaijan during the conflict, and it will be compelled to pay compensation for the substantial socio-economic damage inflicted on Azerbaijan.

Conclusion. As a result of Armenia's policy of aggression, the ecology, biodiversity, forests, and greenery in the occupied territories of Azerbaijan were brutally destroyed, burned, and our natural resources plundered. Alongside the socio-economic plunder of Azerbaijani lands, Armenia also committed ecological terror. The ecological terror in the occupied territories, the deprivation of water for the population living in the frontline areas, the blocking and pollution of border rivers, and the deterioration of reservoirs due to a lack of

technical maintenance, placing surrounding settlements and hundreds of thousands of people at risk, constitute acts of aggression by Armenia against Azerbaijan. Azerbaijan restored justice after thirty years. By ending the occupation, it also prevented the ongoing massive ecological terror. Ultimately, among all "frozen" conflicts in the post-Soviet space, only the Armenia-Azerbaijan conflict found a successful resolution through military-political and diplomatic means, thanks to the unity of the Power-People-Army in Azerbaijan. Conflicts in the South Caucasus pose a threat to the national security of regional states. The more securely the national security, territorial integrity, state sovereignty, and the legal rights of ethnic minorities residing in the Caucasian states are defended, the greater the significance of the vitality of the economy, politics, and culture in the overall Caucasian priorities. Intercultural and interfaith dialogue among peoples in the South Caucasus can lead to the resolution of conflicts. Azerbaijan is a tolerant and multicultural state. Ethnic and cultural diversity in the country is regulated by a policy of multiculturalism. The implementation of multiculturalism as a state policy in Azerbaijani society is associated with the name of the national leader, Heydar Aliyev. The policy of multiculturalism, carried out by the worthy successor of Heydar Aliyev's political course, President Ilham Aliyev, is an integral part of the country's democratic development and the protection of citizens' rights and freedoms. While multiculturalism has failed in many Western countries, the Azerbaijani state has declared multiculturalism as its state policy. President Ilham Aliyev stated, "For us, multiculturalism is state policy and our way of life." The establishment of the Baku International Multiculturalism Center by a decree of President Ilham Aliyev on May 15, 2014, is a sign of the development of tolerance and multiculturalism in the country. The Baku Process, along with the organization of a "round table" on "Intercultural Dialogue" with representatives from over ten European countries as well as members of the Organization of Islamic Cooperation, is a clear demonstration that multiculturalism is a state policy in Azerbaijan. The proposal made by President Ilham Aliyev during his speech at the 65th session of the UN General Assembly in September 2010 to hold the World Forum on Intercultural Dialogue in Baku has led to the transformation of the Baku Process from a regional initiative to a global movement. Azerbaijan has hosted the I, II, III, and IV World Forums on Intercultural Dialogue in partnership with UNESCO, ISESCO, the UN Alliance of Civilizations, the Council of Europe, the North-South Centre of the Council of Europe, and the UN World Tourism Organization. Today, Azerbaijan is hosting many international events, one of which is the United Nations Climate Change Conference to be held in Baku from November 11 to 22, 2024. This conference, known as COP (Conference of the Parties to the UN Framework Convention on Climate Change), will be the 29th UN Climate Change Conference. It should be noted that COP 28 was held last year in the United Arab Emirates, while COP 30 will be hosted by Brazil in 2025. On December 25, 2023, based on a decree from the President of Azerbaijan, 2024 was declared the "Green World

Solidarity Year" in Azerbaijan. The national program adopted by Azerbaijan for socio-economic development by 2030 states that the country is one of clean environment and green growth. Currently, efforts are being made in the country, especially in the areas liberated from occupation, to restore the environment, increase greenery, and ensure the efficient use of water resources and sustainable energy sources. The large-scale restoration and reconstruction processes being carried out in the liberated territories incorporate innovative approaches such as "smart city" and "smart village," alongside environmental protection and the establishment of forests and greenery. Additionally, the Karabakh and East Zangazur economic regions, as well as the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic, have been declared green energy zones. Despite the development of the oil and gas sector in our country, the creation of green energy sources and their transportation to global markets is currently one of the primary directions of our state's energy policy. The project for the mutual coordination of energy systems between Azerbaijan, Kazakhstan, and Uzbekistan (Green Corridor) is under development.

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